

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

Discover NASA science by observing the total solar eclipse.

PASSPORT TO FUN!

Some NASA resources and activities contain eclipse imagery.

DALLAS ARBORETUM

Total Solar Eclipse

April 8, 2024

Learn more
[go.nasa.gov/
EclipseSafety](https://go.nasa.gov/EclipseSafety)

Location

Dallas, Texas

Partial Begins

12:23 PM CDT

Totality Begins

1:40 PM CDT

Maximum

1:42 PM CDT

Totality Ends

1:44 PM CDT

Partial Ends

3:02 PM CDT

Hands-on Activities

Earn your NASA take-home materials by completing at least five activities. Then bring your passport to the Exit Station to receive your take-home materials.

1. Total Solar Eclipse Selfie Station

Take a selfie in front of the NASA Inflatable and scan the QR code to learn how to safely observe the total solar eclipse.

2. Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

Decorate your solar viewing glasses, which you need to safely view the partial phases of the total solar eclipse.

3. Predict the Corona Art

During the total phase of the solar eclipse you will be able to see the Sun's outer atmosphere, the corona. What do you predict you will observe?

4. Total Solar Eclipse Map Pinhole Projector

Solar viewing glasses are just one tool you can use to experience a solar eclipse. Try pinhole projectors to observe how the shape of the Sun changes.

5. Solar Boundary-Heliosphere Demonstration

Come see how the solar wind forms a protective "double bubble" around our solar system & learn how you can make a model of the heliosphere at home.

6. Ancient and Modern Sun-Watching

Find your birthday sunrise on a Chaco Canyon horizon & see with your hands using tactile images of the Sun's corona from throughout human history!

7. Eclipse Button and Sun Clock Crafts

Participate in crafting a button and a Sun clock all the while discovering how your local library serves as a center for scientific exploration!

8. Cloud Cover Estimation

Estimate the percentage of cloud cover on eclipse day and learn how the changes in sunlight during the eclipse can affect solar-powered processes.

9. Explore NASA's Astromaterial Samples

Delve into the captivating world of meteorites, Moon rocks, and learn about the collection of solar wind samples gathered from our Sun by NASA.

10. Test Your Eclipse Knowledge

Participate in an interactive eclipse game and share your thoughts and experience with others on our eclipse experience board.